

20- × 15-cm spacing. Plant height, flowering duration, and yield/ plant were recorded for the main crop. Ability to produce ratoon tillers and flowering behavior of the ratoon were the bases for selecting suitable varieties.

Entries with plants less than 100 cm tall were favored for ratooning, since the main crop was grown under controlled conditions and at higher fertilizer rates (100-22-42 kg NPK/ha) for maximum yield. Nine entries were identified for further study (see table).

RAU4057-35-20, Leuang Yai 148, and C924-9 have semidwarf plant type, high yields, and 1% ratooning ability. Their ratoons flowered the end of Oct,

Ratooning ability of semidwarf photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties. Chinsurah, India, Nov 1986.

Entry	Source	Main crop			Ratooning ability (%)	Ratoon flowering date
		Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (g/plant)		
SPR7292-0-0-0-1	IRSWON	83 ± 4	155	20 ± 7	86	25 Sep 1987
RAU4057-35-20	IRSWON	77 ± 2	136	8 ± 4	100	29 Oct 1987
Leuang Yai 148	IRSWON	77 ± 2	144	20 ± 7	100	29 Oct 1987
IR13149-43-2-P	IRSWON	96 ± 4	153	16 ± 4	100	3 Oct 1987
RTN90-4	IRSWON	96 ± 3	158	11 ± 4	100	26 Oct 1987
TKM9	IRDWON	93 ± 2	123	8 ± 4	100	17 Oct 1987
IR38787-26-2-1-2	IRDWON	100 ± 5	127	9 ± 3	100	18 Oct 1987
NC500	IRDWON	96 ± 7	161	6 ± 4	100	26 Oct 1987
C924-9	IURYN (M)	87 ± 6	140	19 ± 6	100	31 Oct 1987

probably because the lines have shorter critical photoperiod. SPR7292-0-0-0-0-1 planted in late Sep, followed by

IR13 149-43-2-P in early Oct. These dates are more or less desirable for establishing the next crop in Nov. □

Effect of high temperature on rice spikelet fertility

Xu Yunbi, Shen Zongtan, and Shi Chunhai, Agronomy Department, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou, China

An abnormally high percentage of Empty spikelets in first crop indica rice occurs in ricefields south of the Yangtze River when flowering takes place in the heat of July. Daily maximum temperatures of 35.5-38.9 °C 1-20 Jul 1988 in Hangzhou lowered rice yields.

We studied the effect of high temperature on spikelet fertility by using different seeding dates to result in

Spikelet fertility at different heading dates.^a Hangzhou, China, 1988.

Variety	Spikelet fertility (%) at heading date		
	27 Jun	1 Jul	5 Jul
Yuanfengzao	93.9 a (15)	84.3 b (15)	76.8 c (15)
Erjiunan 1	89.1 a (11)	80.5 b (15)	34.9 c (10)
Zhe 85-2	88.2 a (15)	87.2 a (15)	76.2 b (15)
Guangluai 4	85.3 a (8)	78.5 b (15)	70.5 c (15)
Zaolian 31	85.2 a (15)	74.3 b (15)	68.5 c (15)
Erjiufeng	79.6 a (7)	78.4 a (15)	58.1 b (15)

^a Figures in parentheses are sample sizes. In a w, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

different heading dates. Spikelet fertility percentage (SFP) was measured on 7-41 randomly selected plants, 3 panicles/plant, for each cultivar and each planting date.

SFP differed significantly among plants with different heading dates from the same cultivar. SFP at normal temperatures 24-28 Jun was higher than at high temperatures 2-14 Jul (see table

Relationship between mean spikelet fertility percentage (Y) of varieties with the same heading date and mean maximum temperature 3 d after heading (X) ($r_{YX} = -0.9570$, $Y = 73.47 - 0.44X$). Cultivars: 1 = Erjiufeng, 2 = Zhefu 802, 3 = Erjiuqing, 4 = Guangluai 4, 5 = Zhong 83-49, 6 = Erjiunan 1, 7 = Yuanfengzao, 8 = Zhe 85-2, 9 = Zaolian 31, 10 = Ainanzao 39, 11 = Guiluai 8, 12 = Zhuxi 26, 13 = Guangliuzao, 14 = Qingganhuang, 15 = Zhuyunnuo, 16 = Ezao 6, 17 = IR58, 18 = IR28, 19 = IR50.

and figure). Yuanfengzao and Zhe 85-2 that headed at >35 °C had higher SFP (76.8, and 76.2, respectively) than Erjiunan 1 and Erjiufeng (34.9 and 58.1,

respectively).

There was a significantly negative correlation between SFP and mean daily maximum temperature (MMT) 3 d

after heading. SFP decreased with increasing MMT. The critical day for significantly decreased SFP was 30 Jun, when MMT was 35.9 °C for 3 d. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Using silica gel desiccant to dry rough rice samples

P. A. Clarke, Overseas Development Natural Resources Institute (ODNRI), Culham, Abingdon, Oxon OX14 5PR, UK; and M. A. Quasem, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

The method and rate by which rough rice is dried changes the characteristics by which grain quality is judged. We have developed a method that achieves high standardization of large numbers of small samples of grain (less than 1 kg). It is based on the sorptive capacity of a special grade of silica gel mixed directly with field-wet rice.

Intermediate density (ID) grade silica gel is dried, cooled, mixed with field-wet rice in the ratio 1:2 by weight, and the mixture sealed in a moistureproof container. After 24 h, the 2 constituents are separated by screening.

The figure shows the linear regression of field (input) moisture content on residual (output) moisture content within 20–30% wet basis for the model

$$Y = 4.17 \times 0.38; r = 0.91, p = 0.01.$$

Effect of contact mix with ID silica gel on rice input and output moisture content.

Grain quality was measured as grain breakage on milling. The table compares gel-dried samples with sun- and air-dried samples. The gel technique produced

results at least as good as, and some better than, traditional methods, with higher control and resource optimization. □

Moisture content and milling quality of rice dried in a contact mix with ID silica gel and by air and sun.

Drying process	Moisture content (%)		Milling quality (% brown rice)	
	Initial	Residual	Degree of milling	Broken grain
				BR1
Gel	19.2	12.4	16.1 a	20.2 a
Air	19.2	14.3	15.8 a	21.2 ab
Sun	19.2	14.1	15.9 a	21.7 b
				BR3
Gel	24.6	13.7	13.5 a	10.4 a
Air	24.6	14.1	13.0 a	10.4 a
Sun	24.6	14.5	12.5 a	9.1 a
				BR4
Gel	27.1	14.5	13.2 a	5.0 a
Air	27.1	15.6	13.9 b	5.3 a
Sun	27.1	13.2	13.0 a	5.6 a
				BR10
Gel	28.9	15.2	14.0 a	6.2 ab
Air	28.9	14.8	15.1 b	6.6 b
Sun	28.9	13.9	14.4 a	5.9 a

In a column for a variety, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT at $p = 0.05$.

Disease resistance

Resistance to sheath blight (ShB) in China

Xue-Yan Sha and Li-Hong Zhu, Nanjing Agricultural University, Nanjing, China

ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* [Thanatephorus cucumeris (Frank) Donk] is a major disease in the rice areas along the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River and in South China. In 1985–87, we used Tetep, IET4699, Jawa no. 14, and Yedao as resistance donors and IR9752-71-3-2 as

susceptible parent to study the inheritance of reaction to artificial ShB inoculation at booting by virulent isolate RH-9, collected in Jiangsu Province.

The F₁ of four combinations of moderately resistant and susceptible parents showed intermediate reaction to inoculation; the F₂ distributions tended to be continuous. That implies that resistance to ShB is controlled by multiple genes (see figure). Broad and narrow sense heritabilities estimated from the cross IR9752-71-3-2/IET4699 were $h^2B = 0.516 + 0.0654$ (broad) and $h^2N = 0.373 + 0.063$ (narrow).

Analysis of combining abilities based on the performance of 28 diallelic F_{1s}